

THE IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATION IN ATTRACTING INVESTMENT

Perdeboyev Sulton Nurseytevich

Tashkent State University of Economics.

G-mail: sultonperdeboyev956@gmail.com

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Innovation is the key word today and is the main driver of the most positive changes to achieve goals in all possible fields and levels. This means that the introduction of innovations is the most important point of all activities related to the development of this or that field. Innovation usually establishes a new activity or way of doing things that produces significant improvements over old practices. Innovation is the engine of the modern economy and plays an important role in attracting investment. Innovation and investment are closely related. They mean the introduction of new ideas, technologies and methods into production and business processes, which help to increase the productivity, competitiveness and standard of living of the population. creates opportunities, which makes them more attractive for investors. One of the important aspects of innovation in attracting investments is to create a favorable environment for the development of new and promising areas. Innovative companies and start-ups working in fields such as information technology, biotechnology, clean energy and others can attract investment due to their potential for rapid growth and high returns. It can help create new jobs and develop modern technological clusters. Companies with successful innovation programs with a formal approach perform better and grow significantly faster than those without a formal system—a 3x difference over 5 years—Bain Innovation Performance Study 2013.

Organizations with a formal innovation system and structure will see significant gains; 51% are first to market with most innovations, products and new services.—Accenture US Innovation Survey 2015.

Innovation plays a crucial role in attracting investment for several reasons:

- Innovative products, services or processes give companies a competitive advantage in the market. Investors are attracted to businesses that have a unique proposition and differentiate themselves from their competitors. This difference can lead to increased market share and a higher return on investment.
- Market potential : Innovative ideas often respond to unmet needs or solve existing problems in new ways. Investors are attracted to companies with high

growth potential and large market opportunities. Innovative companies are better positioned to enter new markets or create entirely new markets, which can generate significant returns for investors.

- Long-term Sustainability: Innovation is not just creating new things; It's also about stability and flexibility. Companies that are constantly innovating are better equipped to manage market changes, technological advances, and changing consumer preferences. Investors look for businesses that demonstrate long-term viability and sustainability, and innovation is a key indicator of such characteristics.

Innovation can be attractive to investors, especially if it is supported by public policy and financial incentives. Government programs and research grants, tax credits and other tools help to actively invest in innovative projects. As Edith Widder said, "Research is a tool that drives innovation. Innovations ensure economic growth. Therefore, the most economically and politically powerful countries of the world allocate large amounts of money from their budgets for innovations. As an example, countries that will allocate money for innovation in 2021.

Table 1: Countries that allocated money for innovation in 2021¹

1.	United States	476.5 billion \$
2.	China	370.6 billion \$
3.	Japan	170.5 billion \$
4.	Germany	109.8 billion \$
5.	South Korea	73.2 billion \$
6.	France	60.8 billion \$
7.	India	48.1 billion \$
8.	Great Britain	44.2 billion \$
9.	Brazil	42.1 billion \$
10.	Russia	39.8 billion \$

Table 2: the countries with the highest rating in the world according to the data of the international innovation rating of 2022.²

1.	Switzerland
2.	United States Of America

¹ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/732247/worldwide-research-and-development-gross-expenditure-top-countries/>-Countries that will allocate money for innovation in 2021.

² https://www.wipo.int/global_innovation_index/en/ - GII Index 2021 Report

3.	Sweden
4.	Great Britain
5.	Nitherland
6.	South Korea
7.	Singapur
8.	Germany
9.	Philandia
10.	Denmark

Figure 1: Components of the GII index³

In the above infographic, the GII (Global Innovation Rating Information) sub-index: five types of input components provide the innovative activity of the national economy.

covers ements. These components determine the aspects of the environment that support the development of innovations in the economy. The overall score of the GII is equal to the average value of the input and output sub-indices.

Each component is divided into three indicators, including each indicator divided into individual items - 81 in total. Each country was scored on its respective normalized score ranging from 0 to 100.

³ <https://mininnovation.uz/info/global-innovatsion-indeks> - Components of the GII sub-index

Currently, innovation is becoming one of the most characteristic features of economic development. Recently, this name is exotic, unknown and even reminded me of something not so clear even among professionals, but now the innovation itself and its concepts are rapidly conquering the world. The international capital market, which plays a significant role in the innovation process and turns innovation into a strategic resource for companies, is expanding, and new financial structures are helping it in this regard. The experience of developed countries shows that innovation is often hindered by people's direct negative attitudes and attitudes. However, a paradoxical situation is developing in Uzbekistan, that is, the whole society expresses positive attitude and support to innovative processes.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, Innovation means the future. If we start building our great future today, we should start it on the basis of innovative ideas and an innovative approach.

It should also be noted that on September 29, 2022, the report of the "Global Innovations" index was published. Uzbekistan ranked 86th among 141 countries in the Global Innovation Index in 2021. In 2022, it rose 4 places among 141 countries and took 82nd place and became the leader of Central Asia and Central Asia. and ranked 3rd among South Asian countries after India and Iran.

Table 3: 2022 Global innovation rating of the Republic of Uzbekistan ⁴

The Republic of Uzbekistan is in the Global Innovation Index			
t/r	Companents	2022	
		Rating	Place
1.	Quality of institutions	57,3	63
2.	Human capital and research activities	30,8	65
3.	Infrastructure	41,7	74
4.	Market development	39,9	60
5.	Business development	25,3	74
6.	Science and technology	17,9	80
7.	Creative products	7,7	102

⁴ <https://mininnovation.uz/info/global-innovatsion-indeks> -2022 Global Innovation Index rating of the Republic of Uzbekistan

In order to achieve this result, the large-scale reforms in the field of science and innovation in our country in recent years, as well as the special attention paid by the head of our state to the development of the sector, deserve special attention.

Currently, large-scale changes and structural reforms are being carried out in all sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan. The implementation of such reforms is directly based on the investment process in the country, the innovation of the state's investment policy, its priorities are being carried out rapidly. In particular, many normative legal documents adopted in Uzbekistan and reflected in the draft laws widely discussed in social networks. In our country, there are regulatory legal documents for engaging in innovative activities or implementing innovative works in the field of economy and other innovative activities.

Decision No. PQ-3698 of the President of our country dated May 7, 2018 "On measures to improve the mechanisms of introducing innovations into economic sectors and sectors" has created great opportunities and the integration of science and science is important in the development of the economy. It is also known to us from the economies of developed countries in the world.

Table 4: Relevant main regulatory legal documents on Innovative Development activities adopted in Uzbekistan⁵

No	Name of received document	Adopted body	Number and date of received document
1	On additional measures to encourage the application of innovative projects and technologies to production	Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan	PQ-916 No. 15.07.2008
2	On measures to further improve the activities of the Academy of Sciences, the organization, management and financing of scientific research works	Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan	PQ-2789 dated 17.02.2017
3	On measures to further strengthen the infrastructure of scientific research institutions	Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan	PQ-3365 dated 01.11.2017

⁵ <https://lex.uz/docs/-4910391> - Relevant main regulatory legal documents related to innovative development activities

	and develop innovative activities		
4	On the organizational measures of the implementation of innovative projects and the rapid integration of departmental information systems	Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan	PQ-3673 dated 18.04.2018
5	On the organization of the center of advanced technologies under the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan	Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan	PQ-3674 dated 04/19/2018
6	On measures to further improve the system of practical implementation of innovative ideas, technologies and projects	Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan	PQ-3682 dated 27.04.2018
7	On measures to create conditions for the development of active entrepreneurship and innovative activities	Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan	PQ-3697 dated 05.05.2018
8	On measures to improve the mechanisms for introducing innovations into economic sectors and sectors	Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan	PQ-3698 dated 07.05.2018
9	On measures to create effective mechanisms for applying scientific and innovative development and technologies to production	Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan	Issue 24, 12.01.2018

Summary:

In short, the importance of innovation in investment lies in its ability to stimulate growth, create competitive advantage, attract investment, and disrupt traditional industries. This is what allows investments to change the world and

have a real impact. Innovation is the lifeblood of investments. Without it, a company or startup is just another small business trying to survive in a crowded market. Innovation sets companies apart and gives them a competitive edge that leads to rapid growth and success. In modern companies where innovations are introduced, we can see a 2-3 times increase in wages and a 2 times increase in productivity compared to traditional companies, especially since many are the first to market with innovative projects, products and new services. Therefore, it is an important task for the state to support innovations and create favorable conditions for their development.

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